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Safe and sustainable-by-design: The case of nanomaterials

Effie Marcoulaki, System Reliability and Industrial Safety Laboratory, National Centre for Scientific Research "Demokritos", P.O. Box 60037, Agia Paraskevi 15310, Greece,
emarcoulaki@ipta.demokritos.gr

1. Introduction to SSbD

Safe and Sustainable-by-Design (SSbD) principles have emerged as a critical component of the European strategy for safe and sustainable chemicals and materials (ECSS, 2020), to safeguard health and the environment within a Safe Innovation Approach (SIA) (Shandilya et al., 2021). SSbD and SIA encourage the exploration of alternative advanced materials and production processes, within a proactive framework that places an emphasis on incorporating safety and sustainability considerations into the early stages of innovation. Early assessment of risks is key to these approaches, so that developers can identify opportunities to reduce adverse impacts on human health and the environment throughout the entire life cycle of chemicals and materials (Florin, 2023). SSbD can integrate green chemistry principles to promote the development of safe, biodegradable or recyclable chemicals (Furxhi et al., 2023), go beyond the traditional goals of circular economy for reduce, reuse, recycle (Apel et al., 2023), and consider societal and economic aspects (Cassee et al., 2024).

The effort to propose a standardised procedure for SSbD innovation that the industry would adopt voluntarily is still ongoing. Alternatively, the adoption of SSbD could be promoted through regulatory pressures and/or consumer demand for sustainable practices (Tarraco et al., 2021) as part of eco / green innovation approaches. The new eco-design regulation aims to establish updated standards for green products, enhancing their circularity, energy efficiency and other aspects of environmental sustainability in the EU market. This applies to the assessment of existing chemicals as well as the criteria for developing new SSbD products according to the ECSS (EcoR, 2024).

To assist the implementation of SSbD for Chemicals and Materials, the JRC has recently proposed an Implementation Framework and reviewed available tools for sustainable management, including LCA tools for environmental impact or social-LCA (Caldeira, 2022). Recently, Apel et al. (2024) outlined a roadmap for application of SSbD in industrial operations, and highlighted stakeholder needs in the key areas of research, skills and education, and knowledge sharing, emphasizing the need for early, pragmatic SSbD implementation.

2. The case of nanomaterials

Nanotechnologies and nanomaterials are key enabling technologies for European industry, offering significant potential to tackle societal challenges in the 21st century. Ensuring their sustainable production and use requires understanding and effectively managing potential risks along the industrial innovation value chain. Assessing the risks of nanomaterials, including nanoforms, is challenging and requires specific provisions (Schwirn et al., 2020) due to their unique features. These include the diversity in the nanomaterial physical and chemical composition, their surface functionalization and structural properties, as well as the variety of their alternative configurations (Blekos et al., 2023).

Over the past decades, significant European funding has been allocated to studying the safety of materials at nano-scale and developing validated frameworks for the assessment, management and governance of risks and specific to nanomaterials and nano-enabled products. The European NanoSafety Cluster (NSC) was established to enhance collaboration between European projects focused on the safety of nano-enabled materials and technologies, addressing toxicology, ecotoxicology, exposure assessment, interaction mechanisms, risk assessment, and standardization

efforts (Savolainen et al., 2013). The current volume of research has provided data, protocols, models etc. to aid the risk assessment of new nanomaterials. Efforts are still needed to advance our understanding of the diverse adverse effects caused by nanomaterial exposure (Marcoulaki et al., 2021; Mancardi et al., 2023) and particularly the long-term environmental and health impacts until end-of-life stages (Nizam et al., 2021).

Practical operationalization of SSbD requires clear definitions, terminology and criteria, targeted training, strategic plans for collaboration and protection of intellectual property across industries, academia and regulators (Apel et al., 2024). Standards are essential to support public policies and guide the industry toward adopting sustainable practices and environmentally friendly innovations, and provide a framework that ensures green innovations are effectively implemented and aligned with long-term sustainability goals (Scapolo et al., 2015). Recent advancements on nanomaterial-related standards, include the development of Test Guidelines by the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD, 2022), guidance and policy reports by the Joint Research Centre, and documentary standards from ISO/TC 229 Nanotechnologies¹ and CEN/TC 352 Nanotechnologies² (Rauscher et al., 2023). Currently, CEN/TC 352 is also developing a standard for the SSbD concept dedicated for nano-scale materials and nano-containing products (Cassee et al., 2024).

Responding to the need for global collaboration, the International Network Initiative on Safe and Sustainable Nanotechnologies (INISS-nano) brings together leading researchers across nano-safety research fields, aiming to improve the understanding and regulation of nanomaterials' impacts on health and the environment (Pogany et al., 2024). On the side of specialized training, there is need for vocational training dedicated to SSbD. At the moment, there are postgraduate courses in Europe focusing on nanomaterials and SSbD principles as part of their curriculum. Additionally, projects like SbD4Nano³ provide e-learning modules and resources aimed at operationalizing SSbD in nanotechnology supply chains.

3. Conclusions

SSbD is integrated into the European strategy for chemical safety and sustainability, and aims to serve as a catalyst for innovation, pushing the boundaries of traditional chemical design to include environmentally benign alternatives and improved manufacturing processes (ECSS, 2020). By addressing safety and environmental concerns proactively and embracing a life cycle approach, SSbD not only enhances the marketability of products but also supports the broader goals of environmental sustainability and public health. As research continues to advance in this area, the potential for SSbD to reshape industries for the better remains substantial.

Efforts to implement the SSbD strategy to innovative nanomaterials and nano-enabled products include the development of guidelines, standards and regulations at EU and international level. These are supported by long and ongoing research to enhance understanding of nano-specific hazards, and develop regulatory-relevant assessment tools for risk assessment and management. Knowledge gaps remain in long-term environmental and health impacts of nanomaterials, demanding further interdisciplinary research. However, all the outcomes discussed here provide the framework and drive for adoption of the SSbD approach in nanomaterial innovation, and act as a paradigm for implementation and operationalization of SSbD to other advanced materials.

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